

ISic0767

Funerary honours for Aulus Mevius Zethus

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated before 1965 from a Roman villa in the vicinity of Halaesa, in contrada Lancinè

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Soprintendenza di Siracusa

Physical Description

A marble slab, rectangular in form with a moulded surround (dimensions not recorded). The slab is broken on the right side.

Dimensions

Height ? cm

Width ? cm

Depth ? cm

Layout

Two lines of Latin text filling the available field. The second line is slightly indented (and so centred?).

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Neatly engraved and well proportioned letters with modest serifs. M has hastae slightly off vertical; E has bars of equal length; Z has long and curving horizontal strokes; the third T in line 2 is extended above the line. Words are separated by comma-like triangular interpuncts which find frequent parallels in the inscriptions of Halaesa.

Letter heights:

Line 1: ? mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: ? mm

Text

1. A(ulo) · Mevio · Zeth[o][---]
2. Patrono · ex · test[amento][---]

Apparatus

Text from photograph

Translation (en)

(Set up for) Aulus Mevius Zethus [---] patron, in accordance with his will [---]

Commentary

The location of this stone is not currently known. Manganaro proposed reading *optimo* at the end of line 1 and that the name of a freedman, responsible for setting up the honorific, should stand at the end of line 2. The extent of the stone that is lost is unknown. The erection of posthumous honours or funerary monuments in accordance with a will is a common practice (a Sicilian example from Catania in ISic0380 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0380>]). It is possible that ISic0768 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0768>] (dedication to Concordia by a *sevir*) was set up by the same Aulus Mevius Zethus, or a related individual, since the cognomen [-]ethus is preserved there. The gens Mevius is also attested at Taormina ISic0282 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0282>] and at Termini (ISic0198 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0198>] , ISic0199 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0199>]); cf. Facella 2008: 288. The form of this text suggests a date in the first or second century AD.

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Photo from Manganaro 1989 fig.86